

Mediating role of Engaged Living in Mitigating Loneliness of Adult Retiree Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 06,2025</p> <p>Accepted: September 08,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Trait Gratitude, Loneliness, Engaged Living, Mediation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17080599</p>	<p><i>This study was undertaken in rural setup to study mediating role of engaged living in mitigating loneliness in adult retiree teachers. Population of the study comprised of adult retired teachers. Only those retiree teachers were selected whose age was more than 60 year. Snow ball sampling technique was used for sample selection. Total 180 male teachers were selected. Data was collected through standardized questionnaire. Three questionnaires were used for data collection. One questionnaire was for trait gratitude, second questionnaire was for loneliness and third questionnaire was used for engaged living. Data was collected through personal visit and analysed through SPSS using regression analysis. It was found that there was significant relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness. Significant relationship was found between trait gratitude and engaged living. It was found that Engaged living and loneliness were significant related. Engaged living significantly mediated relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness. Four hypotheses were formulated and all were accepted at 95% confidence level.</i></p>

Introduction

Aged people are facing many challenges and problem in their lives. Such people experiencing decline in mental and physical health and feel continuous pain in joints and muscles. Aged people also experience loneliness due to loss of family members, loss of dear and close friend or some other disruptive stressor (Hill, 2011). Prevailing of such situation enhances aged people engagement to change circumstances and adapt to meaningful life (Wong, 2016). Therefore it is essential that old age may be consider not a burden in itself but an opportunity to adjust to existing situation and take advantage of it (Pavlickove&Nagyova, 2016).

In a research study, among European Union, the high ratio of loneliness was found in Netherland and it was placed at third position in this regard (Eurostat, 2017). Loneliness increases with increase in age, it was found 63% in people having 85 year old and only 41% in middle-aged persons. Psychologists believe that loneliness is the result of two factors, one is the aversive experiences which result in negative way of behavior like sadness and anxiety (Menec, et al, 2019). Second factor is the shortcomings in social relationship. Absence of intimate relationship and social relationship leads to emotional loneliness and social loneliness (Brimelow&Wollin, 2017).

Many risk factors are responsible for loneliness of an individual such as serious health problem, loss of social network, loss of intimate relationship, betrayal of friends, bad conduct of family members (Gan et al. 2015). Sometime personality factors and genetic disposition are considered major risk factors of loneliness. Empirical evidence shows that loneliness has negative effect on mental and physical health of an individual. Continuous loneliness result in depression, mental stress and cardiovascular disease (Christiansen, Larsen &Lasgaard, 2016 &Kharicha et al., 2017). If loneliness persist for long time, it may result in suicide ideation (Huang et al., 2019). Besides these risk factors some other factors are also responsible for loneliness. According to Richard et al., (2017) unhealthy lifestyle behavior is associated with loneliness. Smoking, obesity, less physical activities, limited social contact, also result in loneliness and psychological distress (Hegeman et al., 2018).

It is of immense importance to pinpoint relevant psychological resources that may prevent or lessen loneliness. This current research study is based on the relationship between loneliness and trait gratitude. This study will also focus on the mediating effect of engaged living and psychological flexibility in the association between loneliness and trait gratitude in adults of over 50 year and older. This mechanism proved to be useful for decreased psychological problem and to be beneficial for mental and physical health of the individuals (Trompetter et al., 2013; Jans-Beken et al., 2017). Current research study aims of unveiling possible ways of mitigating loneliness with possible and important role of trait gratitude, engaged living and psychological flexibility.

Trait gratitude is an important psychological resource that may lessen or prevent loneliness in old or middle-age. Trait gratitude may be define as the tendency to acknowledge any thing or to recognize benefits from other with

grateful expression or emotions. Expression of grateful emotion may not only foster personal well-being but it also positively affects others' well-being. In different research studies, negative relationship was determined between loneliness and trait gratitude (Caputo, 2015). Positive emotions decrease individual mental stress and motivate persons to be optimistic and broaden their life perspective. This can increase engagement in meaningful activities which further furnish value-oriented and meaningful life (Ni et al., 2015).

People showing trait gratitude, exhibit pro-social conduct in the beginning but after some time, these behavior results in the creation of social relationship due to grateful behavioral expression. Such behavioral expression builds and strengthens intimate friendship (Algoe&Zhaoyang, 2016). Gratitude means to be focused on the qualities, behaviors, traits and values of other people to build emotional attachment with other.

Trait gratitude also connects people more closely as a result of feelings, thoughts, emotions and behavior. Different research studies concluded that people who are alone and have no grateful expression, feel loneliness. Such persons have weak social relationship in society, and it result in the lack of trust over others (Lamster et al., 2017). Lonely person is less involved in discussion or pay less attention to other people.

According to Shi et al (2016), alienated people express behavior leading to withdrawal behavior in the society. The role of trait gratitude cannot be denied in the encouraging of older persons in building intimate relations with others (Caputo, 2015).. It also help older individual to make strong existing bonds with friends and to find new friends. Trait gratitude is considered a positive and important characteristic that can mitigate feelings of loneliness and build strong social relationship.

In a research study by Von -Faber et al (2001), it was determined that during aging process, absence of feeling of loneliness, feeling of gratefulness and a strong circle of social contact, are some important factors fostering well-being and emotional expression in older adults. Psychological flexibility role is of crucial importance in the pathway from gratitude to loneliness. Psychological flexibility concept means the ability of an individual to cope with adverse situation with flexibility. Coping adverse situation with flexibility promote meaningful engagement and personal valued activities.

Boman et al (2017) determined that psychological flexibility of individual decrease with passage of time or increase in age. Older adults exhibit low quality of psychological flexibility as compared to adults. To some extent, adults and middle-aged individuals can strengthen psychological flexibility easily as compared to older and aged persons. There is a gap about the role of psychological flexibility in the relationship between loneliness and trait gratitude. There is no or little evidence about relationship between psychological flexibility and trait gratitude. According to Fredrickson (2004), increase in psychological flexibility is directly related gratitude and well-engaged life. Gratitude is considered as skill that enhance life engagement and result in positive emotions and feeling of satisfaction. It also enhances and promote psychological flexibility of individuals (Hill, 2011). Some limited research studies concluded that feeling of loneliness decrease with psychological flexibility (Gardiner et al, 2018).

Individual with engaged in life possess less feeling of loneliness. Engaged life means recognize and accepting one's own abilities, characteristics and personal values and sharing it with other people. Engaged living result in committed work, completion of work, personal satisfaction and sharing of personal experience (Trompeter et al., 2013). Engaged living results in the accomplishment of personal life goals. Individuals who are engaged in life have a sense of purpose in life and utilize time to create opportunities. Sense of purpose don't vanish with life-span but it remains in older age. Older-aged individual can contribute positively by providing them with meaningful activities in life. This will sustain sense of relevance in older adults and will also sustain their social values. Engaged living directly affects mental, physical, social and emotional health of older persons (Irving, 2017).

Some previous research studies declared negative relationship between loneliness and engaged living. Individual deficit in personal values and characteristics for engaged living face problems in building relationship with other individuals and consequently, such individuals feel loneliness. Individuals who are engaged in meaningful activities have high level of positive affect and, on the other hand, individual deficit in meaningful life engagement experience low level of negative affect. This result in reduce feelings of loneliness (Ditcheva et al, 2018). According to Trindade et al (2016), engaged living result in decreased level of distress and it is clear in the form feeling of loneliness. Older individual held social values dear and these are rooted more in them (Petkus&Wetherell, 2013).

Objectives

- To determine relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness
- To find relationship between trait gratitude and engaged living
- To explore relationship between engaged living and loneliness
- To find mediating effect of engaged living in relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness

Hypotheses

- H₁: Trait gratitude has significant relationship with loneliness
 H₂: Trait gratitude has significant relationship with engaged living
 H₃: Engaged living has significant relationship with loneliness

H₄: Engaged living mediates relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness

Methodology

Quantitative research design was used for conducting this research study. This research study was conducted in the rural setup of District Karak. After retirement, different people face a loneliness problem. Some people face social loneliness and some face emotional loneliness. This study aimed to study mitigating loneliness in retiree teachers: meditating role of engaged living. Population of the study comprised of retiree teachers. Snowball sampling technique was used for sample selection. Total 180 retired teachers were selected keeping in view access to the population. Those adult teachers were selected whose age was more than 60 years and only male retired teachers were selected.

Three variables were used in this study. Trait gratitude is used as dependent variable, loneliness is treated as dependent variable and engaged living is used as mediating variable. Data was collected through survey questionnaire. Three questionnaires were used for collecting data from the selected sample size. First questionnaire was for trait gratitude. For trait gratitude, Jans-Beken et al (2015) questionnaire was used. It comprised of 16 items. Five point Likert scale was used ranging from (1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree). Second questionnaire was for engaged living. It also comprised of 16 items and five point Likert scale was used ranging from (1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree). Third questionnaire was used for loneliness and for this purpose, De Jong Gierveld&Tilbug (1999) questionnaire was used. This research instrument has two dimensions which are emotional loneliness and social loneliness. It comprised of 11 items. Data was analysed using SPSS.

Results

To analyze data, regression analysis statistical test was used. Following were the major findings related to hypotheses

H₁: Trait gratitude has significant relationship with loneliness

Table 1

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F
1	.466	.217	.215	96.47

Predictors: (Constant), Trait Gratitude (TG)

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1					
Constant	14.34	.934		15.36	.00
TG	.379	.039	.466	9.822	.00

Independent Variable: Trait Gratitude

Dependent Variable: Loneliness

Data in table 1 indicates significant relationship between independent variable (trait gratitude) and dependent variable (loneliness). R value is .466 and R² value .217 which shows that independent variable (trait gratitude) explains 21.7% dependent variable. F statistic value is 96.47 which show model fitness. In the coefficient table, β value is .466 which determines that a unit change in our independent variable will bring a positive change in dependent variable. In the table, t value is 9.82 and p value is .00 which is less than .05. It indicates that trait gratitude has significant relationship with loneliness. Hence our hypothesis H₁ which states that there is significant relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness as accepted at 95% confidence level. Hence first condition for Mediation is fulfilled which is that there should be significant relationship between independent variable and dependent variable.

Table 2

H₂: Trait gratitude has significant relationship with engaged living

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F
1	.212	.045	.042	16.32

Predictors: (Constant), Trait Gratitude (TG)

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1					
Constant	19.78	.983		20.13	.00
TG	.164	.041	.212	4.04	.00

Independent Variable: Trait Gratitude

Dependent Variable: Engaged Living

Table 2 describes relationship between trait gratitude and engaged living. Engaged living is treated as dependent variable. Data in model summary table shows that R value .212 and R² value .045 which indicates that our independent variable explains 4% of dependent variable (engaged living). F value is 16.32 which shows model fitness. In coefficient table, β value is .212 and t value 4.04. P value is .00 which is less than .05 ($p < .05$). This value determines that there is significant relationship between trait gratitude and engaged living. It is also cleared that second assumption for mediation is also met which is that there should be significant relationship between independent variable and mediating variable. Our hypothesis H₂ which states that there is significant relationship between trait gratitude and engaged living is accepted at 95% confidence level.

Table 3

H₃: Engaged living has significant relationship with loneliness

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F
1	.328	.108	.105	42.08

Predictors: (Constant), Engaged Living (EL)

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients t	Sig.
1	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	15.27	1.26		12.07 .00
EL	.345	.053	.328	6.48 .00

Independent Variable: Engaged Living

Dependent Variable: Loneliness

Table 3 describes regression analysis result of engaged living and loneliness. Engaged living is treated as independent variable and loneliness is treated as dependent variable in this regression analysis model. R value is .328 and R² value is .108. This R² value indicates that our independent variable (engaged living) 10.8% explains dependent variable (loneliness). F value is 42.08 which show model fitness. β value is .328 and t value is 6.48. P value is .00 which is less than .05. It is cleared from these values that there is significant relationship between engaged living and loneliness. The third assumption for mediation is also fulfilled which states that there should be significant relationship between mediating variable and dependent variable. Hypothesis H₃ which describes that there is significant relationship between engaged living and loneliness is accepted at 95% confidence level.

Table 4

H₄: Engaged living mediates relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F
1	.466	.217	.215	96.47
2	.522	.272	.268	64.94

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients t	Sig.
1	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	14.34	.934		15.36 .00
TG	.379	.039	.466	9.822 .00
2 (constant)	9.34	1.32		7.04 .00
TG	.337	.038	.415	8.85 .00
EL	.253	.049	.241	5.13 .00

Independent Variable:

Trait Gratitude (TG)

Dependent Variable:

Loneliness

Mediating Variable:

Engaged Living (EL)

Table 4 indicates result of mediating effect in relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness. Result of the model table summary shows significant difference in data after entering the effect of mediating variable. Before entering mediating variable, R value is .466 and R² value is .217. F value is 96.47. When mediating variable is treated in the model, all these values change. After entering mediating variable, R value changed into .522, R² value also changed and new value was .272. F value changed into 64.94. Changes in these values indicates that mediating variable (engaged living) significantly mediated. Result of the coefficient table also presents changes in values after entering mediating variable. After entering mediating variable (engaged living),

β value changed into .241 and t value also changed. P value is .00 which indicates that engaged living has significantly mediated relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness. Our hypothesis H_4 which states that engaged living significantly mediate relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness.

Discussion

This current study examined mediating effect of engaged living in relationship between trait gratitude and engaged living. A positive and significant relationship was found between trait gratitude and loneliness. This finding was not consistent with the result of the previous study. People who felt less gratitude in everyday life, face loneliness (Feng, 2011). Gratitude plays significant role in increasing happiness, social desirability and life satisfaction. Gratitude works as a social benefits for promoting and enhancing social bonds which leads to less loneliness among individuals.

In previous research studies (Bracklin, 2002), gender differences were found related to loneliness. It was found that women are more vulnerable as compared to men. The reason may be that women develop a way of thinking which is connected and depends on sense of being with others. Loneliness role is of immense important regarding the formation and maintenance of social relationship. Loneliness is an unpleasant emotional experience which result of not having what one's wants. Loneliness is considered as feeling of unwanted solitude, isolation and emptiness.

This positive association between trait gratitude and loneliness endorsed Broaden and Build theory of positive emotion. According to this theory, trait gratitude enhances communication among people and as a result people come close together (Algoe, 2012). Increase gratitude result in helpfulness of others and it promote social relationship among individuals. Hence it is assumed that trait gratitude is an important potential psychological resource that works as catalyst in lessening loneliness in adults.

It was found that there engaged living fully mediated relationship between trait gratitude and loneliness. This suggest that when adult persons are engaged, the experience less loneliness. Engagement may be social engagement, emotional engagement and peer engagement, all these work for mitigating loneliness of adult people. If adult people receive social support and emotional support from family members, from social circles, then they can live a happy and prosperous life and they will experience less loneliness.

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